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**Non-equilibrium and Coherent Systems
in
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GEOMAGNETIC MONITORING: EXPERIMENTS AND PROSPECTS IN BIOLOGY AND MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

Numerous investigations indicated a substantial influence of geomagnetic disturbances, including different phases of Solar activity, upon growth of bacteria and cell cultures and the dynamics of infection diseases and other pathologies. We report here some medical observations pointing to the effects of a geomagnetic environment upon the cardio-vascular system.

Numerous investigations indicate the influence of Solar activity and geomagnetic disturbances upon living objects. Among those we should point first of all to the pioneer studies by A.L. Chizhevsky (1976). He compared the epidemic dynamics of cholera, diphtheria and other infectious diseases within XIX with the Solar activity cycles. It appeared that the epidemic bursts correlated with the decreasing periods of the Solar cycles. The duration of Solar activity cycle is about 11 years. It correlates with Conrad Wolf's numbers of sunspots formation rate. A bacteriologist Velhover while studying diphtheria dynamics came to the similar conclusion.

At the present time we live during a decreasing period of Solar activity: the last Solar activity cycle started in the year 1986 and reached its maximum in 1991. At the present time, in a complete correspondence with Chizhevsky and Velhover's predictions we experience the uprise of cholera, diphtheria and other epidemic diseases. According to Velhover's ideas, at the maximal phase of Solar activity the bacteria are to a great extent "saturated" with energy, thus being not so infectious. The increase in their aggressiveness correlated with a decline of energy "nutrition" during the decreased Solar activity period. In any case, this obvious correlation points to substantial links between Sun emission and other accompanying geomagnetic phenomenae and the physiological state of bacterial cells. A similar dynamics have been also reported by

Gorshkov, Savidiva (1972) and Vladimirsky et al., (1972).

Recent investigations indicated significant influences of geomagnetic disturbances upon growth and differentiation in cell cultures (Belisheva et al., 1993). These studies were carried out at the temporary geophysical monitoring station, situated in a high latitude region of the Earth protected from industrial electromagnetic noises. A decrease of the rate of DNA synthesis followed by its compensation within the subsequent cell cycles, an increase of hyperplastic processes, formation of huge cell aggregations, appearance of giant nuclei and polynuclear cells have been observed under the conditions of high geomagnetic activity. Periods of sharp changes in the geomagnetic activity coincided with the changes in the rhythms of DNA synthesis within all of the cell lines under investigation. The effects of the alternated variations of electromagnetic field of a very low intensity upon the bioluminescent activity of photobacteria have been also shown (Berzhanskaya et al., 1993). The effects were dependent upon the cells physiological state and the fields frequencies and were found to be of a non-thermal origin. High and low electromagnetic fields frequencies acted synergetically.

Chernoshchekov and Lepekhin (1993), showed that the growth rate of typhoid bacteria increased after magnetic storms by 3 to 6 orders of magnitude. The authors observed the appearance of new mutations which were resistant to the well-known antibiotics and supposed that under these geomagnetic situations the danger of epidemy is increased.

Let us pass from bacteria to higher organisms. Chibisov et al. (1992) have studied on rabbits six physiological parameters of the cardio-vascular system, including systolic and diastolic blood pressure and the inner pressure in left and right cardiac chambers. The acidal-basical balance and the level of blood free lipids have been also measured. The results have been compared with the simultaneous geomagnetic situations. The biological data were obtained at all phases of the Earth geomagnetic storm. At the initial and the main phase of the storm the normal circadian rhythms according to all of the cardio-vascular parameters disappeared. Desynchronization increased at the storm period and led to an abrupt drop of cardiac output, degradation and distortion of cardiomyocytes (Kudrin & Zhdanov, 1984).

Andronova et al. (1982), in the course of the study of the influence of the various natural factors upon healthy population living in the high latitude showed that the changes of the magnetic field of the Earth were of an utmost importance. By analysing the everyday excretion of 17-oxycorticosteroids, the authors came to a conclusion that the periods of a high level geomagnetic activity preceded the increase of the rate of hormone excretion within 24-48 hours and that the growth of geomagnetic activity lead to the rise of blood coagulation and to the increase of the platelets number.

In experiments on patients with ischemic heart disease the blood hypercoagulation have been registered within the first day of the magnetic storm (Kochetkova, 1974). Our own investigation of a capillary blood flow of patients with ischemic heart diseases showed a high dependence between the flow and the magnetic storms (Gurfinkel et al., 1993). In the first day of the magnetic storm the pathological changes of a capillary flow were detected in 71.8% patients with acute myocardial infarction (in 73.6% of men and in 69.2% of women). We detected also the appearance of a perivascular oedema, aggregation of red blood cells, as well as a delay and slowing down of a capillary flow. Similar changes have been detected in the patients with angina pectoris.

From the year 1991 at the Laboratory of Magnetobiology in the Moscow Central Railway Hospital a continuous monitoring of a geomagnetic environment is being performed. A new class of devices indicating magnetic storms have been created in the Institute of Terrestrial Magnetism, Ionosphere and Radio Wave Propagation of Russian Academy of Sciences (Lubimov et al., 1993). High sensitivity of these instruments gave us a possibility to indicate a magnetic situation in any region of the Earth within a real time scale. A geomagnetic monitoring may be of help for the patients who need drug protection and special protection in a shield-room during magnetic storms.

Although the real mechanisms mediating the geomagnetic influences upon living organisms are still obscure, the very fact and the medical importance of these effects are out of question. It seems highly probable that the ultraweak photon emission from the organisms may serve as both an intermediate link and an indicator of these influences.

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